

CHARACTERISTICS OF WORD GROUPS IN THE FRENCH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The French language is composed of eight primary parts of speech, each essential to sentence structure and meaning. These include nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, articles, prepositions, and conjunctions. This article explores the characteristics of word groups in the French language.

Keywords: parts of speech, nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, articles, prepositions, conjunctions, gender (masculin/feminine), number (singular/plural), the noun suffix, special suffixes, the determiner, special words, *descriptive adjectives* (adjectifs descriptifs), *possessive adjectives* (adjectifs possessifs), *interrogative adjectives* (adjectifs interrogatifs), *demonstrative adjectives* (adjectifs démonstratifs), personal pronoun, impersonal pronoun, the definite article, the indefinite article, the partitive article.

Introduction. Words are categorized based on their parts of speech. In the French language, there are eight primary parts of speech.

They are:

1. **Nouns** (noms): Words that name people, places, things, or ideas. *Example: chien (dog), France (France), liberté (freedom);*
2. **Adjectives** (adjectifs): Words that describe nouns or pronouns. *Example: grand (tall), bleu (blue), heureux (happy);*
3. **Verbs** (verbes): Words that express an action or a state of being. *Example: manger (to eat), être (to be), courir (to run);*
4. **Adverbs** (adverbes): Words that modify verbs, adjectives, or other adverbs, often indicating time, manner, place, or degree. *Example: rapidement (quickly), ici (here), très (very);*
5. **Pronouns** (pronoms): Words that stand in for nouns or a noun phrase. *Example: il (he), celui (that one), nous (we);*
6. **Articles** (articles): An article is a word that modifies a noun in a particular way, by stating whether the noun is specific, unspecific, or partial. *Example: un, une (a/an) des (some), le, la, les (the), du, de la, de l' (some) ;*

7. **Prepositions** (prépositions): Words that show the relationship between a noun (or pronoun) and other words in a sentence.

Example: sur (on), sous (under), entre (between);

8. **Conjunctions** (conjonctions): Words that join words, phrases, or clauses.

Example: et (and), mais (but), ou (or).

Main part. This article will explore the characteristics of word groups in the French language.

NOUNS. A word group that denotes the names of animate and inanimate objects, actions, qualities, abstract concepts is called a noun. As is known, the concept of gender does not exist in the Uzbek language. In Russian, there are three genders – masculine, feminine and middle gender. In French, nouns are divided into two: *le masculin* and *le féminin*. In dictionaries, they are abbreviated as *m* and *f*. It should be remembered that the gender of a noun in Russian does not always coincide with the gender of a noun in French.

The gender of nouns in animate objects is expressed in the following ways:

1. By changing the noun suffix;
2. By adding special suffixes;
3. By changing the determiner;
4. By leaving special words.

VERBS. As in many languages, verbs in French have different forms for the different functions they perform in sentences. It is traditional to present verb forms in paradigms. *Simple forms* are made up of stems to which endings are attached. *Compound forms* are made up of forms of the auxiliary verbs avoir and être plus a past participle. *Double compound forms* are made up of forms of the compound auxiliary verbs avoir eu or avoir été plus a past participle.

ADJECTIVES. Adjectives (les adjectifs) describe the qualities and characteristics of a noun, they describe how someone or something is. They always accompany the noun they describe, and the endings of an adjective always agree with the noun in terms of gender (masculine or feminine) and number (singular or plural). There are four types of adjectives:

1. *Descriptive adjectives* (adjectifs descriptifs). they tell what kind of person or thing the noun is: *une grande maison des hommes intelligents.*

2. *Possessive adjectives* (adjectifs possessifs). they tell whose noun it is: *Mes parents ton livre.*

3. *Interrogative adjectives* (adjectifs interrogatifs). they ask which noun it is:

Quel livre as-tu perdu? Quelles chaussures veux-tu acheter?

4. *Demonstrative adjectives* (adjectifs démonstratifs) They point out things (“this”/ “that” / “these”/ “those”): *Cette classe est intéressante. Je n’aime pas ces fraises.*

ADVERBS. Adverbs usually indicate quantity, time, place, intensity, and/or manner (“how”). Adverbs are invariable. They modify:

1. Verbs. Adverbs which modify verbs are placed directly after the verb: *Il chante mal. Mes cousins vont arriver bientôt.*

2. Adjectives. Adverbs which modify adjectives are placed directly before the adjective. They usually indicate intensity: *Robert est complètement stupide. Le chien est très grand.*

3. Other adverbs. Adverbs which modify other adverbs are placed directly before the adverb they modify. They usually indicate intensity: *Lili parle trop rapidement. Tu fais assez bien la cuisine.*

4. Whole sentences. Adverbs which modify a sentence are usually placed either at the beginning or at the end of the sentence: *Maintenant, vous allez faire du ski. Vous allez faire du ski maintenant.*

PRONOUNS. Pronouns are words that substitute for nouns. There are many different kinds of pronouns, but they can be divided into two main categories: personal and impersonal.

ARTICLES. One of the eight parts of speech, an article is a word that modifies a noun in a particular way, by stating whether the noun is specific, unspecific, or partial. There are three types of French articles and they all agree in gender and number with the nouns they modify: *the definite article, the indefinite article, the partitive article.*

PRÉPOSITIONS. Prepositions indicate a relationship between a noun and other nouns. Prepositions are forms like *de, à, dans, en, sur, par, pour, avec, au-dessus de, du haut de, à cause de,* and so on.

CONJUNCTIONS. Conjunctions join together words or parts of sentences. A few of the most common conjunctions in French are: *ou* (or), *et* (and), *que* (that), *parce que* (because), *mais* (but), *ni* (nor).

Conclusion. Words are categorized into parts of speech, with the French language comprising eight main types. Each plays a crucial role in sentence structure and meaning. They are: *nouns* (un nom or un substantif), *verbs* (un verbe), *adjectives* (un adjectif), *adverbs* (un adverbe), *pronouns* (un pronom), *articles* (un article), *prepositions* (une préposition), *conjunctions* (une conjonction). Certain parts of speech are variable, which means their form changes: *articles, adjectives, nouns, verbs.* Understanding the specific features of

word group classification in the French language is highly important for translation and language learning.

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